

EFFECTIVENESS OF ACTION GAMES IN THE PROCESS OF COMPLEX TRAINING OF YOUNG FOOTBALL PLAYERS.

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Anatization: One of the main tasks is the selection of young players, their comprehensive training, and the formation of their physical qualities, life skills and abilities.

One of the important tools in the complex training of young football players is the use of selected types of action games and their application in the training process.

Key words: Young players, action games, development, physical fitness, training, physical qualities.

Today, the process of globalization is developing rapidly. Also, the fact that we live in the modern information age requires a new way of thinking and a new approach to every job from every citizen.

Nowadays, the field of physical education and sports is rapidly developing in our Republic, like all other fields. It is a clear expression and proof of our opinion that modern open and closed facilities are being completed in remote villages of our republic and are being handed over to the population for use.

The creation of such conditions by our government is of great importance for the growing young generation to grow up physically healthy and mature, to be brought up mentally mature, to mature in the spirit of sane thinking and loyalty to the Motherland. Such conditions that are being created increase the responsibility of every employee working in the field of physical education and sports and impose great tasks.

As a result of such conditions created in accordance with the world's requirements, we can cite as an example the results and achievements of our athletes on the international arena.

In particular, the Decree No. PF-6099 dated October 30, 2020 of the President of our Republic Sh.M. Mirziyoev "On measures for the wide implementation of a healthy lifestyle and further development of mass sports" for the development of our country, to protect the health of an educated, highly moral and cultured population and serving as an important enabler and roadmap for strengthening implementation.

We can conclude that in this decree, among other sports, in particular, the organization of public sports competitions in football is an important main

direction, and the attention to football in our country is at a high level. As proof of our opinion, in particular, in the development of the sport of football in our country, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 18, 1993 "On measures to further develop football in the Republic of Uzbekistan" and dated January 17, 1996 "On measures to fundamentally improve the principles of football development and organizational foundations in Uzbekistan" We should mention the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. M. Mirziyoyev on March 16, 2018 "On the further development of football" and emphasize that these decisions are of great importance in the further development of the football sport.

It is one of the most important tasks to train young football players to become physically healthy, intellectually and spiritually mature due to the mastery of national movement games, to prepare them for the initial complex through movement games, to develop and strengthen their physical qualities, and to further increase their interest and respect for the history, culture, and traditions of Uzbekistan.

At the initial stage of preparation for working with young players, it is appropriate to use a set of tools aimed at developing the initial complex, acquiring all-round physical fitness, strengthening health and harmonious development, acquiring various skills and competencies, and teaching them the basic principles of football game techniques and tactics.

The task of preparation at this time is primarily to form the movement functions of young players (strength, speed, endurance, agility and dexterity, as well as the ability to control their movements in time, in the air and according to the level of muscle exertion are the main components of the movement function). Great attention should be paid to training the speed of movements, because in childhood and adolescence there are ample opportunities to train this most important physical quality. The use of action games is an effective tool for developing and strengthening these qualities.

Sport has a decisive power in creating a healthy environment, in developing the young generation in all aspects, physically and mentally. The reason is that we are still moving towards development, and there are still many educational and educational problems that need to be solved on our way.

For example, in the development and strengthening of physical training and physical qualities of young football players, folk games and action games, which are considered to be invaluable traditions and unique values of our people, play an important role in physical education and sports training. After all, their

physical qualities such as strength, quickness, agility, dexterity, agility, and flexibility are developed and strengthened together with mental, aesthetic, labor, and moral education through action games.

Each action game has its content form (structure) and methodical feature. The content of action games consists of the following: the theme or content (expressive or conditionally thought out work, game plan) is the action and rule that enter the game to achieve the goal.

The form of action games is to have a wide choice of ways to achieve the set goal, to organize the movement of game participants. Game participants act individually or in groups to achieve their personal interests in the same games, while in others they protect their team, their team's interests. Also, for the game, the players stand in different formations or forms (scattered or scattered, in a circle, in a row, in a line).

The form of the game depends on the content. The characteristic of the game from the methodological point of view depends on its content and form. Action games are unique from a methodological point of view: a) liveliness; b) to act independently in achieving the goal according to the limited rule; c) act with creative initiative in accordance with the rule; g) fulfillment of separate roles in the game, compliance with its content, a certain level of interaction of the game participants in the team is established; d) a sudden change in the game, which requires players to take the initiative and react quickly; e) competitive elements in the game increase the excitement (emotionalnost) in the game and require full effort; j) pitting the interests of opposing parties against each other in solving "Disagreements" that arise in the game creates a high level of enthusiasm.

Action games are not only a tool, but also a method of physical education of a child.

In particular, football players' relay, Passing and kicking the ball, Kicking the ball from the circle, Kicking the ball, Attacking, Carrying the ball in the head, Relay of football elements, Juggling, Passing two balls, Going around the posts, Agile goalkeeper, Heading. , sitting the ball back, dropping the ball over the fence, kicking with a shot and using a number of action games serve as an effective tool in the process of initial complex training of young players, in developing and strengthening their technical and tactical actions.

In the process of comprehensive physical training of young football players, instead of some mandatory exercises, selecting national folk games, dances, physical exercises and national sports, determining their size, direction and

effectiveness, A. Navoi's Mahbub-ul-kulub, Farkhod and Shirin, U. Khayyom's Navro'znama, Abu Ali Ibn Sina's Al-Qanun, Kaikovus's Qabusnama, and Mahmud Kashgari's Devon-u-lugatit Turkish works serve as excellent sources.

Searching for young players and talents growing up in the remote areas of our republic, carrying out selection work, giving them relevant instructions and concepts, revealing and demonstrating their talents and abilities, creating conditions for them is an important and important task for every sports official and coach. one of the urgent tasks.

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